

**LINGUISTIC AND SPIRITUAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SOME
PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN TAHIR MALIK'S "HUMAN
PROPERTY".**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11123883>

It is known that the phraseological units related to literary speech are expressed in the dictionary of phrases. Phrases specific to the language of live conversation are not included in this book. If we look at it from this point of view, it can be observed that many expressions used in the work of Tahir Malik do not have a place in the dictionary.

We can see that the artist used about 70-75% of the expressions used in his work as in the vernacular, i.e. exactly.

In a work of art, the creator selects and uses various tools available in the language according to the purpose. The units that contribute to increasing the aesthetic value of the work show the skill of the creator. A skilled creator, along with existing units, invents new expressions himself or gives a new "color" to the content of lexemes in the language based on the speech situation. Some of them contribute to the enrichment of the vocabulary of the language based on the norms of the literary language over time, and some remain specific to a particular speech.

Tahir Malik also followed in the footsteps of the great masters of words, and with his deep philosophical views, sense of words, and unique creativity, he brought new, individual, beautiful findings and expressions to the language. He created them based on the internal capabilities of the language and managed to increase the content and attractiveness of his works. For example, there is an expression in the Universal language to turn a blind eye. This phrase is used to express meanings such as "to ignore knowingly", "to pass away".

serves. In the work, the writer effectively used the first meaning of this phrase. But we cannot turn a blind eye to this horror (yes, we call it horror, evil). Are there few or many people who dress up their fathers or mothers in their old clothes while inviting guests to the table of donations to the extent that amazes the mind? (page 58); Incidents like this happen, even if they are rare, and it is

not typical for a Muslim child to turn a blind eye to them. We meet many people in life who honor their parents, and it makes our hearts happy. (page 58)

The writer used the phrase "to lend a hand" a lot. This phrase is universal in the language "to direct one's hand as far as possible to get something directly",

"extending one's hand in greeting", "sexual feeling deal with", "try to use for one's own benefit

to do", "to appeal for salvation", "to help" is expressed in such meanings. For example, isn't it our duty to give them a helping hand and help them get rid of unbelief? (page 5) The expression "hand in hand" means "joining", "uniting". Let's see: the flood of bad education is closing, isn't it time to join hands to save our psyche, our children, and our loved ones from this flood of trouble? Hand in hand is not just empty talk. The Poles proved it in practice. For one day, for one hour, the people of the whole country took to the streets, joined hands, formed a living chain and expressed their unanimity in the fight against drug addiction. (page 16)

The phrase to see well is "to love", "to be in love", means "to like", "respect". Tahir Malik effectively used this phrase in his work. For example, "One of the companions of Rasulullah (s.a.w.) met me, grabbed my shoulder and said: "I love you." I said to that person: "May Allah, who made me love you, love you too!" - I said. I would not have told you that I love you if I had not heard the hadith of the Prophet (pbuh) saying: "If a person loves someone, let him know that he loves him." they said." (p. 37); But because the son is the continuation of the lineage, the father also feels special joy. The reason for rejoicing should not be interpreted as discrimination against girls. Because in Islam, it is not considered correct to separate children, that is, to love one more and the other less. (page 53)

There is an expression in the vernacular. This expression has shades of meaning "to face", "to look in one direction". For example, those who are fascinated by the fact that Europe is advanced in science and culture. We cannot directly follow their opinion today. Because in the field of education, both America and Europe have declined in the next hundred years. (page 16); The most terrible thing is that they were drunk inside a temple, and they turned to idolatry like the people of that temple. (page 26); There are two ways to know a person worthy of a friend. One is that if his friend's situation is difficult or he faces poverty, he does

not turn away from him, but he does not miss his wealth. Another is to visit his friend's children, relatives and friends even after his death. (page 138)

To come to the world usually means "to be born". We said in the previous chapter that life is an exam, let's return to this topic: where there is an exam, there is duty, responsibility, responsibility. A person is born with this responsibility. (p. 10)

There are many such examples.

In a work of art, the creator selects and uses various tools available in the language according to the purpose. The units that contribute to increasing the aesthetic value of the work show the skill of the creator. A skilled creator, along with existing units, invents new expressions himself or gives a new "color" to the content of lexemes in the language based on the speech situation. Some of them contribute to the enrichment of the vocabulary of the language based on the norms of the literary language over time, and some remain specific to a particular speech.

Occasional meaning is an artificial meaning that is not specific to the meaning of the lexeme in the language, and is created as a result of some person (author) giving a new "color" to the content of this lexeme based on the speech situation. It has an individual character and is understood only in context.

In the folk language there are expressions like "The man of the street". Tahir Malik used a new original phrase on behalf of the male community: Unfortunately, some of us have our hearts tied to the streets. (p. 9) This phraseological unit gave rise to the meanings of street lover and street lover.

When reviving a certain image, the artist also creates unique individual phrases such as "depends on his mind", "watching with the mind's eye", "headache category", "his love began to affect his mind", which are the impressiveness of the work. , enriches the language with new expressions while contributing to increasing the aesthetic spirit.

Such advices are the guidance given to us by the wise. It is, so to speak, a plan for a person's self-education. How he will implement the plan now depends on his mind. (p. 12)

That's why a person needs to observe his surroundings with the eyes of his mind and dare to leave bad circles. There is no point in trying to wash and purify yourself while standing in the swamp. (page 12)

Suppose there are six women working in one room. One of them is a book reader, and others get headaches when they say books. (p. 109)

After a few more fights, the ul zat's love began to affect their minds. (page 30)

We can also find the phrase to be equal to a sweet soul only in Tahir Malik's work: If you want to know the true language of a friend, try to make him angry with your tongue or frown. If you want to know how much love your friend has for you, ask him what he likes best. If he doesn't frown even after these two things, then such a friend should be treated like a sweet soul. (page 121)

Our analysis shows that Tahir Malik used expressions very efficiently. In general, the expression of expressions in an artistic work is very wide and diverse. This can be clearly seen in Tahir Malik's work "Human Property". In this work of Tahir Malik, there are many expressions used to show the mental states of people. If the work has no place, the phrase is not used. They play an important role in enhancing image quality.

Tahir Malik's work reminds of a rippling ocean full of jewels and pearls. The more you dive into it, the more you feel its unique beauty and richness. The author's works are enriched with unique artistry, charm, and philosophical expressions, which are not found in other creators, contribute to the enrichment of the treasure of our national language and culture.

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